

HAEMATOLOGY AND SERUM BIOCHEMISTRY PARAMETERS AS INDICATORS OF THE MOST COMMON CANINE VECTOR BORNE DISEASES IN RN MACEDONIA

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ABSTRACT

Canine vector borne diseases (CVBD) are one of the major health issues in Macedonia, with potential fatal outcome. Different pathogenic organisms, transmitted by blood sucking arthropod vectors, cause the diseases. Most commonly present CVBD in Macedonia are: canine ehrlichiosis, heartworm disease, anaplasmosis and leishmaniasis. Infected dogs can present variety of clinical signs, depending of the stage of the disease and the affected organs. The aim of this study was to present most commonly found haematology and serum biochemistry alterations in dogs with CVBDs. For that purpose, we analysed 40 dogs, divided in 4 groups depending of the disease. Haematology and serum biochemistry analyses were analysed for each dog. The results revealed moderate normocytic normochromic anaemia with elevated kidney parameters as well as hypoalbuminemia and hyperglobulinemia in patients with leishmaniasis. Thrombocytopenia was marked haematology parameter for patients with ehrlichiosis, while elevated ALKP was present in dogs with heartworm disease. These laboratory parameters can be used in conjunction with the clinical findings as indicators for further necessary diagnostic tests for CVBD in dogs.

Key words: canine vector borne disease, hematology, serum biochemistry.

Introduction

Canine vector borne diseases (CVBDs) represent an increasing global threat, in human and veterinary medicine, due to their constant spread from endemic regions to new areas, exposing new populations to previously unknown infectious agents and being especially challenging to veterinarians for diagnosis. CVBDs comprehend a number of various pathogenic organisms that are transmitted mainly by blood sucking arthropods. Climate changes and pet travel are one of the factors that increase the geographical range of many vector borne diseases, some of them with potential zoonotic concern (Genchi et al., 2011).

In RN Macedonia several vector borne disease are described and often diagnosed in every day veterinary practice, including heartworm (*Dirofilaria immitis*), canine leishmaniasis (*Leishmania infantum*), canine ehrlichiosis (*Ehrlichia canis*) and anaplasmosis (*Anaplasma spp*) (Atanaskova Petrov et al., 2021; Stefanovska et al., 2012).

Heartworm disease is an important mosquito-borne disease in dogs caused by the filarial nematode, *Dirofilaria immitis*. The adult forms reside in the pulmonary arteries, causing inflammation and endothelial damage. Canine heartworm disease can manifest a wide range of symptoms, from mild asymptomatic disease to exercise intolerance, chronic cough and congestive heart failure (Polizopoulou et al., 2000).

Caine anaplasmosis and ehrlichiosis are tick-borne diseases. *E.canis* causes a wide variety of clinicopathological changes: fever, lymphadenomegaly, thrombocytopenia, bleeding tendencies,

nonregenerative anemia etc. and can be recognized as acute, subclinical or chronic. Clinical manifestation of canine anaplasmosis usually is unspecific, revealing fever, anorexia, bleeding tendencies (Michael, 2020).

Canine leishmaniosis, caused by *Leishmania infantum*, is a zoonotic disease transmitted by a phlebotomine sand fly vector (Maia et al., 2015). The presence or absence of disease is determined by the host's immune response and the balance between the humoral and the cellular immune responses, so the disease can be present as a subclinical infection, or as dermatitis, alopecia and keratoconjunctivitis with lymphadenomegaly (cutaneous form), to severe renal failure with severe organ damage and potentially fatal outcome (visceral form) (Maia et al., 2015).

Various diagnostic procedures in detecting CVBDs are available to date, but many times due to owner's financial limitation, veterinarians are limited with the laboratory analyses. Detailed history, combined with the physical examination findings (hepatomegaly, splenomegaly, lymphadenopathy, pale mucosa, fever, dehydration) and some initial haematology and serum biochemistry results, might help identifying the possible pathogen/s and indication for further specific testing (blood smear, rapid immunochromatographic tests, ELISA or PCR) (Michael, 2020).

The aim of this study is to present the mostly found hematology and serum biochemistry parameters alterations in canine patients with CVBD such as leishmaniasis, ehrlichiosis, anaplasmosis and heartworm.

Materials and methods

Design of the study

This study is performed at overall forty (n=40) dogs admitted at the University Veterinary Hospital in Skopje. All of the patients have anamnesis and clinical manifestation indicative for CVBD. Based on the rapid test results, patients were divided in 4 groups, each containing 10 dogs positive on one disease (ehrlichiosis, anaplasmosis, heartworm or leishmaniasis).

Blood sampling

After clinical examination and anamnestic data, blood samples were taken by venepuncture of *v. cephalica* for complete blood count (CBC), serum biochemistry analyses as well as rapid immunochromatographic testing.

Haematological and biochemical analysis

Complete blood count was analysed on haematology analyser Exigo (*Boule, Sweden*), while the biochemical parameters (ALT, AST, ALKP, Urea, Creatinine, Total protein, Albumin) were analyzed on automatic spectrophotometric analyzer *ChemWell 2910*, (*Awareness Technology INC, USA*), according to manufacturer's instructions (*Human, Germany*).

Immunochromatography

All dogs were tested for CVBD using serum samples with rapid antigen test kit (CaniV-4 LEISH, *Bionote, South Korea*) according manufactures instructions. The Anigen Rapid CaniV-4 Leish Test Kit is a chromatographic immunoassay for the qualitative detection of *Dirofilaria immitis* antigen, antibody against *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* / *Anaplasma platys*, antibody against *Leishmania* and antibody against *Ehrlichia canis* in canine serum, plasma or whole blood.

Statistical analysis

Results from haematology and serum biochemistry parameters were analysed using basic descriptive statistics for each group, with following parameters: average value (AV), standard deviation (SD), reference minimum (MIN) and maximum (MAX). Comparisons on haematological and biochemical parameters between groups were made by using Kruskal-Wallis Test and Mann-Whitney Test with significant level set on $p < 0.05$. All results were analysed on program Statistica 8.0.

Results

Dogs that had clinical manifestation and positive rapid test result for leishmaniosis (n=10), were of different breeds (2 Samoyed dogs, 4 mixed breed, 2 golden retrievers and 2 German shepherds), median age was 5.3 years (min. 3, max 8 years), while according to gender there were 6 male and 4 female. The laboratory results showed moderate nonregenerative anaemia (RBC $3.32 \pm 0.96 * 10^{-12}/l$, HGB 8.23 ± 2.29 g/dl, PCV $17.82 \pm 4.5\%$), with elevated kidney parameters (Urea $30,70 \pm 20.41$ mmol/l and Creatinine $352,62 \pm 274.12$ μ mol/l) and hypoalbuminemia ($18,48 \pm 6.96$ mmol/l), compared with reference values for dogs (Table 1).

E. canis positive dogs (n=10) were of different breeds (3 mixed breed dogs, 2 Husky dogs, 1 German shepherd, 3 Labrador retrievers and 1 Samoyed), with median age of 5.1 (range of 1-8 years), regarding gender 7 male and 3 female. Mild anaemia (RBC $4.66 \pm 1.2 * 10^{-12}/l$, HGB 11.33 ± 3.42 g/dl, PCV $28.11 \pm 8.13\%$) and moderate thrombocytopenia (PLT $95.4 \pm 97.93 * 10^{-9}/l$) were present in the group of dogs positive for canine ehrlichiosis. Serum biochemistry results revealed mild hypoalbuminemia (20.72 ± 4.63 mmol/l) and hyperglobulinemia (49.10 ± 12.21 mmol/l) (Table 2).

The *Anaplasmosis* positive group (n=10) consists of 5 male and 5 female dogs, median age of 5.9 years (range 2 to 10 years old), from different breeds (2 Labrador retrievers, 2 maltese dogs, 5 mixed dogs and one pug). The results from dogs positive on anaplasmosis did not reveal any specific changes in the blood and serum analyses. Only mild anaemia RBC ($5.39 \pm 0.67 * 10^{-12}/l$) was present, while the other parameters had mild to moderate individual alteration within the group (Table 3).

D. immitis positive dogs (n=10), were mainly mixed breed (7 mixed breed, 1 Staffordshire terrier, 1 German shepherd and 1 miniature pincher), with median age of 4.8 years (range of 3-7 years), 7 male and 3 female dogs. Characteristic finding in patients with heartworm disease was increased levels of ALKP (302.57 ± 73.15 U/l). Haematological and biochemical results in this group keep variable trend of changes of examined parameters (Table 4).

Considering Table 5, statistically significant decrease of RBC and increase of Urea ($p < 0.0001$) was present between leishmania group in comparison to ehrlichiosis, anaplasmosis and heartworm group. There was also statistically significant decrease of PLT values ($p < 0.05$) in dogs with ehrlichiosis compared to dogs with leishmaniosis and heartworm, as well as statistically significant increase concentration of ALKP ($p < 0.0001$) in dogs with heartworm compared with dogs with leishmaniosis, ehrlichiosis and anaplasmosis.

Table 1: Results from dogs positive for *Leishmania sp.*.

n=10	RBC *10 ⁻¹² /l	PCV %	HGB g/dl	PLT *10 ⁹ /l	WBC *10 ⁹ /l	LYM *10 ⁹ /l	MON *10 ⁹ /l	NEUT *10 ⁹ /l	ALT U/L	AST U/L	ALKP U/L	Albumin mmol/l	Total protein mmol/l	Globulin mmol/l	Urea mmol/l	Creatinine μmol/l
X*	3,32	17,82	8,23	216,80	16,72	1,80	1,40	12,76	71,11	50,27	151,05	18,48	55,61	37,13	30,70	352,62
SD*	0,96	4,50	2,29	118,26	13,09	1,12	1,13	10,45	27,11	24,44	72,69	6,96	9,25	7,16	20,41	274,12
MIN*	2,03	11,90	5,30	21,00	4,50	0,80	0,30	3,00	32,38	26,26	79,40	5,97	40,37	25,66	6,16	113,28
MAX*	5,09	26,20	12,40	402,00	42,30	3,90	3,40	33,60	125,14	88,91	307,60	29,44	67,09	47,38	61,42	909,47

*X – arithmetic median value, SD – Standard deviation, Min – minimal value, MAX – maximal value.

Table 2: Results from dogs positive for *E. canis*

n=10	RBC *10 ⁻¹² /l	PCV %	HGB g/dl	PLT *10 ⁹ /l	WBC *10 ⁹ /l	LYM *10 ⁹ /l	MON *10 ⁹ /l	NEUT *10 ⁹ /l	ALT U/L	AST U/L	ALKP U/L	Albumin mmol/l	Total protein mmol/l	Globulin mmol/l	Urea mmol/l	Creatinine μmol/l
X*	4,66	28,11	11,33	95,40	14,04	5,07	2,65	5,81	57,60	37,98	109,07	20,72	69,82	49,10	7,84	127,82
SD*	1,20	8,13	3,42	97,39	6,85	2,62	2,62	4,52	26,04	14,89	52,71	4,63	13,38	12,21	5,38	48,16
MIN*	2,31	10,60	4,60	10,00	3,70	2,3	0,70	0,30	26,13	21,06	36,20	14,45	39,65	24,91	4,25	79,78
MAX*	6,52	42,40	16,10	337,0	24,40	9,30	8,10	14,10	98,78	67,83	198,40	28,29	85,79	66,79	22,36	236,98

*X – arithmetic median value, SD – Standard deviation, Min – minimal value, MAX – maximal value.

Table 3: Results from dogs positive for *Anaplasma sp.*

n=10	RBC *10 ⁻¹² /l	PCV %	HGB g/dl	PLT *10 ⁹ /l	WBC *10 ⁹ /l	LYM *10 ⁹ /l	MON *10 ⁹ /l	NEUT *10 ⁹ /l	ALT U/L	AST U/L	ALKP U/L	Albumin mmol/l	Total protein mmol/l	Globulin mmol/l	Urea mmol/l	Creatinine μmol/l
X*	5,39	30,17	12,71	195,40	9,46	2,02	0,85	6,24	60,00	31,29	109,95	21,53	63,32	41,78	6,47	102,42
SD*	0,67	6,08	1,60	108,21	3,91	0,84	0,36	3,39	83,64	12,89	42,54	2,16	6,75	6,82	3,80	42,79
MIN*	4,26	23,50	10,40	35,00	4,90	1,40	0,40	2,70	18,56	19,50	45,30	19,01	48,69	26,73	3,22	44,07
MAX*	6,29	41,60	15,20	317,00	18,10	4,20	1,60	14,50	296,66	63,96	176,10	26,49	71,25	49,67	14,46	198,90

*X – arithmetic median value, SD – Standard deviation, Min – minimal value, MAX – maximal value.

Table 4: Results from dogs positive for *D.immitis*

n=10	RBC *10 ¹² /l	PCV %	HGB g/dl	PLT *10 ⁹ /l	WBC *10 ⁹ /l	LYM *10 ⁹ /l	MON *10 ⁹ /l	NEUT *10 ⁹ /l	ALT U/L	AST U/L	ALKP U/L	Albumin mmol/l	Total protein mmol/l	Globulin mmol/l	Urea mmol/l	Creatinine μmol/l
X [*]	5,87	38,95	14,24	295,30	18,10	2,63	1,49	13,14	77,53	60,28	302,57	22,11	61,19	39,08	5,17	98,83
SD [*]	1,29	10,19	3,50	85,83	5,47	1,10	0,74	5,87	27,67	23,43	73,15	3,89	5,12	7,31	1,64	26,83
MIN [*]	3,66	25,80	8,70	120,00	8,70	0,70	0,50	6,90	41,09	31,46	212,42	16,10	53,64	27,98	2,80	42,59
MAX [*]	7,66	53,80	18,90	416,00	24,90	4,10	2,90	23,90	114,52	95,55	445,40	30,71	69,56	49,51	8,69	135,23

*X – arithmetic median value, SD – Standard deviation, Min – minimal value, MAX – maximal value.

Table 5: Haematology and biochemistry results with basic parameters of descriptive statistic (AV±SD, MIN-MAX)

	Hematology results													Serum biochemistry results												
	RBC 10 ¹² /L	PCV %	HGB g/dl	PLT 10 ⁹ /L	WBC 10 ⁹ /L	LYM 10 ⁹ /L	MON 10 ⁹ /L	NEUT 10 ⁹ /L	ALT U/L	AST U/L	ALKP U/L	ALB mmol/l	TOT PROT mmol/l	GLOB mmol/l	UREA mmol/l	CREAT μmol/l										
Leishmaniosis	3,32±0,96 ^a	17,82±4,5	8,23±2,29	216,8±118,26 ^b	16,72±13,09	71,10±27,11	50,27±24,44	151,05±72,69 ^c	18,48±6,96	55,61±9,25	37,13±7,16	30,70±20,41 ^a	352,62±274,12													
AV±SD	2,03-5,09	11,390-26,20	5,30-12,40	21,00-402,0	4,50-42,30	32,38-125,14	26,26-88,91	79,40-307,60	5,79-29,44	40,37-67,09	25,66-47,38	6,16-61,42	113,28-909,47													
Ehrlichiosis																										
AV±SD	4,66±1,2 ^a	28,11±8,13	11,33±3,42	95,4±97,39 ^b	14,04±6,85	57,60±26,04	37,98±14,89	109,07±52,71 ^c	20,72±4,63	69,82±13,38	49,09±12,21	7,84±5,38 ^a	127,82±48,16													
MIN-MAX	2,31-6,52	10,60-42,40	4,60-16,10	10,00-337,00	3,70-24,40	26,13-98,78	21,06-67,83	36,20-198,40	14,45-28,29	39,65-85,79	24,91-66,79	4,25-22,366	79,78-236-98													
Anaplasmosis																										
AV±SD	5,39±0,67 ^a	30,17±6,8	12,71±1,6	195,4±108,21	9,46±3,91	60,0±83,64	31,29±12,89	109,95±42,57 ^c	21,53±2,16	63,32±6,75	41,78±6,82	6,47±3,8 ^a	102,42±42,79													
MIN-MAX	4,26-6,29	23,50-41,60	10,40-15,20	35,00-317,00	4,90-18,10	18,56-296,66	19,50-63,96	45,30-176,10	19,01-26,49	48,69-71,25	26,73-49,67	3,22-14,46	44,07-198,90													
Heartworm																										
AV±SD	5,87±1,29 ^a	38,95±10,19	14,24±3,5	295,3±85,83 ^b	18,1±5,47	77,53±26,67	60,28±23,43	302,57±73,15 ^c	22,11±3,89	61,19±5,12	39,08±7,31	5,17±1,64 ^a	98,83±26,83													
MIN-MAX	3,66-7,66	25,80-53,80	8,70-18,90	125,00-416,00	8,70-24,90	41,09-114,52	31,416-95,55	212,42-445,40	16,10-30,71	53,64-69,56	27,98-49,51	2,80-8,69	42,59-135,23													

^a Statistically significant decrease number of RBC and increased Urea ($p < 0.0001$) compared with ehrlichiosis, anaplasmosis and heartworm.

^b Statistically significant decrease number of PLT ($p < 0.05$) in dogs with ehrlichiosis compared with dogs with leishmaniosis and heartworm.

^c Statistically significant increase concentration of ALKP ($p < 0.0001$) in dogs with heartworm compared with dogs with leishmaniosis, ehrlichiosis and anaplasmosis

Discussion

Diagnosis of CVBDs can be a challenging task. Often clinicians are forced to limit the diagnostic procedures, due to expensive laboratory equipment, lack of analytic methods and insufficient data. History of the patient, anamnestic data, local epidemiology situation, season, together with the clinical finding can ease the choice for further diagnostic and analytic methods. Hematology and serum biochemistry parameters can additionally help in decision making for additional diagnostic techniques (Irwin, 2014). Based on all previously mentioned criteria about CVBD, overall 40 patients were divided into 4 groups, according to the positivity of the rapid immunochromatographic test result. Laboratory results reflect multipathological systemic failure, so the most of them can be used as benchmarks for determination of CVBD and staging of disease.

Dogs with clinical symptoms and positive immunochromatographic rapid test of *L. infantum*, presented moderate nonregenerative anaemia, uraemia, and hypoalbuminemia associated with hyperglobulinemia. High serum concentration of globulins and the anti-Leishmania antibodies are most likely responsible for depositing immune complexes in the endothelium of the renal vascular system, affecting glomerular perfusion rate and acting as a trigger for developing mesangioproliferative glomerulonephropathy (Ciarabella et al., 1997). This stage of the disease is usually subclinical, so further damage of renal parenchyma can cause irreversible changes in the juxtaglomerular apparatus in the secretion of erythropoietin. Thus, protein-losing nephropathy with hypoalbuminemia and lack of serum concentration of erythropoietin with non-regenerative anaemia can be considered as the main laboratory alteration in the viscera-cutaneous form of leishmaniasis. According to some authors, severe renal damage is the only clinical manifestation of the disease, resulting in uraemia, hypoalbuminemia and non-regenerative anaemia. Many authors reported that renal damage is a consequence of the formation and deposition of immune complexes due to the infection (Ciarabella et al., 1997; Freitas et al., 2012). Presence of mild or moderate anemia is an often finding in dogs infected with *L. infantum* and can be related with bleeding (especially epistaxis), immune-mediated hemolytic process, inflammation process in different organs especially non-pruritic pyoderma and periocular dermatitis, bone marrow with dysplastic process. Aplasia or hypoplasia can be a common finding in dogs with leishmaniasis (Koutinas et al., 1999). Analysis of blood samples in this research revealed expected changes of blood markers, moderate anemia with a wide interval of variation, increase in serum concentration of degradation products, hypoalbuminemia and hyperglobulinemia in conjunction with clinical manifestation and anamnestic data. There was also a statistically significant difference of RBC ($p < 0.0001$) and urea ($p < 0.0001$) in the group of dogs with leishmaniasis compared to the other CVBDs (Table 1). High diversity of many symptoms related with typical and homogeneous blood markers can be considered as a point for further serological or molecular testing.

The group of dogs with ehrlichiosis has an interesting trend of hemato-biochemistry alteration. Many authors reported nonregenerative anemia due to bone marrow hypoplasia, blood loss or peripheral extravascular destruction of the erythrocytes; our study shows similar results (Table 1), mild nonregenerative anemia, but with a marked interval of individual variation (min $2,31 \cdot 10^{12}/L$; max $6,52 \cdot 10^{12}/L$). Many factors can be included in this variable such as stage of disease, immunological status of the dog, previous infection, concomitant disease, age and breed of the dog. Marked thrombocytopenia is a regular finding in canine ehrlichiosis due to immune impairment causing reactive splenomegaly and activation of the macrophage-monocytes system with enhanced immune-mediated platelet destruction, increased sequestration in the spleen (Waner, 2008). Bone marrow can be affected by *E. canis*, thus many of the examined dogs developed pancytopenia in all circulatory

cellular elements due to hypoplastic and dysplastic changes. Intravascular aggregation, adhesion and activation can diminish the life span of platelets and affected primary hemostasis in dogs with ehrlichiosis. In our study, there was a statistically significant thrombocytopenia ($p < 0.05$) in dogs with ehrlichiosis, compared to leishmaniasis and heartworm groups.

The group of dogs with anaplasmosis, presents mild alteration regarding the platelets and red blood cells, although in many studies severe thrombocytopenia was reported in patients with anaplasmosis (Bouzouraa et al., 2016, Ravnik et al., 2009). Rapid test for detection anaplasmosis, does not differentiate two species of *A. platys* and *A. phagocytophillum*, but both of them cause low production of antibodies for immune-mediated sequestration of erythrocyte and thrombocyte in spleen. Some authors revealed similar results about low pathogenicity of *A. platys* infection because of mild clinical symptoms and hematology alterations (Dantas-Torres, 2008). Long-term persistence of anaplasmosis in dogs can be a risk factor for developing immunodeficiency stage or other concomitant diseases.

The group of dogs with heartworm presents marked increase serum concentration in ALKP, while the other parameters present wide variation into the group. Significant increase concentration of ALKP ($p < 0.0001$) in dogs with heartworm explain multisystem organopathy and subclinical stress. This appearance can be explain about different stages of this disease in examined dogs. Microfilariaemia can affect cardio-pulmonary and hepato-biliary system, as well as whole blood, immune system, vascular system and kidney. Systemic multi organ involvement in this disease can provoke production of this enzyme from other organs increasing the serum concentration level. Other reason for increasing ALKP could be intravascular endothelial lesion, due to the microfilariaemia. Tabizi, 2012, reported similar results in patients with *D. immitis*. Evidence of liver damage is further supported by mild elevation in mean ALT and AST values in dogs from this group. These parameters should be followed and treated in patients with heartworm disease.

Hypoalbuminemia was a common finding in all groups because of increasing catabolism of albumins, albumin losing nephropathy and inability for regular production of albumins in the liver. Hyperglobulinemia developed as a normal immune response of infection agent in accordance with dysproteinemia (Purswell et al., 2020).

Conclusion

Obtained results from this study revealed that hematological and biochemical parameters can be considered as biomarkers in CVBDs. Moderate anemia and elevated kidney parameters is regular finding in dogs with viscerocutaneous form of leishmaniasis. Marked to severe thrombocytopenia can be consider as common finding in ehrlichiosis and increased serum concentration of ALKP is useful parameter in heartworm. Hematological and biochemical results in dogs with CVBD in accordance with anamnestic data and clinical condition can use as biomarkers for further molecular testing for confirmation of the pathogen.

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